

University of Helsinki
Faculty of Arts

Final project: Analysis and visualization of museum art collection of Metropolitan Art
museum

Computational Literacy course

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Digital Humanities track

About the data and research questions

For my research project I chose the dataset of 470,000 artworks provided by the Metropolitan Art museum. The dataset is in open access and can be downloaded from the Github: <https://github.com/metmuseum/openaccess> It is a CSV file, the list of the collection items with detailed info, the images are not included. The dataset cannot be used for analyzing world art in general, because it is only one collection, where the artworks were selected on the museum's conditions. Nevertheless, with the help of the dataset we can see, how it can be useful for the museum and what data visualization can be applied for understanding the collection acquisition and regional distribution of art.

The research questions can be formulated as following:

- How the data of art collection can be visualized for representing the collection and providing insights with the help of visualizing tools;
- What are the main bias in the art collection metadata which can be improved for providing better analysis.

This project can be used as a template for museum data analysis and can bring more insights when analyzing the same data from other museums in a chosen region or sphere of art. Same time it can create a template for the datasets, which would fit this type of visualization.

Previous research

Museum data can be collected from museums in various ways, for example, as physical objects, collections of metadata, visitors' activity in virtual museums and offline, etc. In the current project I would like to concentrate on the analysis of representation of the museum collection and the similar research was done by Mark-Jan Bludau, Marian Dörk, Frank Heidmann in their paper "Relational perspectives as situated visualizations of art collections". The goal of the research was to create an appropriate representation of the complex data and to explore the specific context of an artifact and the various relations it may have to other items (Bludau, Dörk, Heidmann, 2021) .

The correct data representation and systematization can help to provide the database for digital museums and recommendations when combined with machine learning, like it was done in the research "Machine Learning and Museum Collections: a Data Conundrum" by L. Noehrer, J. Carlton and C. Jay.

Bias:

- Info in the data lacks standardization, for example, the origin can be marked as “America, probably”. In this case I assumed a probable country as true and removed the “probably” in the OpenRefine.
- The art collection of one museum cannot be seen as the source of insights for art in total, because the circumstances and goals of the museum objects acquisition may vary. Anyway, it can be analyzed as a museum collection only.

Cleaning the data:

- The dataset has multiple categories, and first with the Openrefine I removed columns which are not relevant for the project. For my research questions, I left the following columns: object number, object ID, accession year, object name, object begin date and country.
- Not all objects have all the data mentioned, and in this case I excluded those, which country or date of origin is not mentioned.
- The country of origin is not always mentioned correctly, therefore I unified the names of the countries as follows. In case of same duplicated name I left one, for example United States|United States changed into the United States. From those countries which had a country name with a question mark or mentioned “possibly”, I removed those leaving the name of the country only. I did the same with regions of the countries or old manes, which are not any longer in use. Below are the examples how I modified the names of the countries:

Northern France - France,
 present-day Uzbekistan - Uzbekistan
 Czech Republic or Slovakia - Czech
 Nubia (Sudan) - Sudan
 England|France - England
 probably Iran - Iran
 Northern India - India
 South Netherlands - Netherlands

United States|England - United States. In the case of two countries there can be two ways to clean the data - to exclude this class of items or remove one name. I removed the second name assuming the first name is more reliable. This creates a possibility for bias, but due to the relatively low amount (about 10 objects) it is unlikely to affect the whole pattern.

Additionally I excluded objects, which country of origin had more than two countries and with amount 10 or less in a subclass. After the data cleaning the total amount was 75751 objects, see the csv file MetObjects-genral.

Visualization:

The visualization of the museum object collections were done in RawGraphs programs and for each I created a subset of data based on the main dataset I created on the base of the original data set of MetObjects. The first visualization is the distribution by country. For that visualization I set the text facets for the country of origins in OpenRefine and got the list of 41 countries with the amount of objects over 100. There were plenty of countries with amount of objects less than 100, and I didn't include them to avoid heavy lists and messy charts.

Here I tried two types of charts - bar chart and treemap in order to compare. Below is the traditional bar chart, where we can see that most of the collection items arrived from Egypt, the Unites States and Iran. Other 38 countries have much fewer objects.

Another way to visualize the distribution of the museum collection was the treemap, see the graph below:

The treemap shows the distribution, but unlike the bar chart, it doesn't show the real amount of the objects, which can create the false impression that countries like Germany, Spain, Italy etc had more objects than they did in reality. In this case the bar chart is more informative and provides better insight to the museum collection.

The next visualization is the acquisition by year which shows when the collection acquired more items. Since objects were acquired every year, visualizing it by year will make the graph overloaded. In order to avoid it I created a column in OpenRefine with the decades based on the year column. Then with the help of numeric facets I got the data of acquiring by each decade and created a separate list based on that. For visualizing it I first used the bubble chart, but it wasn't very informative, so I chose the classical line chart.

Graph 3. Acquisition by decade

From the graph we see that the most the collection arrived at the museum in 1910s, declined during the Second World War. There was a second peak in 1970s, and after that the amount of object acquisition slowly declined compared to the first half of the 20th century.

Another goal was to find and visualize categories of the museum objects. This was the most challenging, because the names of the categories are not standard and it can contain different values even if objects can be named the same. For that I did the clustering of the object names two times in OpenRefine and tried to sort the text facets as before, but OpenRefine couldn't do so because the total amount of names of over 13000 was too much to process. After removing the rows with empty names I got the dataset of 36051 objects and uploaded it into R Studio. There I found top 20 most common names and the frequencies and created a chart in Rawgraphs.

Here we can see that most of the common items are dishes like bottles, jars and vases. Large amount of masks and scarabs can be explained by the fact that most of the collection items came from Egypt.

In this visualization I'd like to note the bias, because it doesn't include a big amount of collection items which didn't have description and the description which was present, wasn't standardized or unified. The possible standardization of the object types can help to provide better statistics and even become the base for ontology for Semantic Web.

Analysis and conclusions:

The research and visualization can provide insights to the collection of the museum for now and show the history of artwork acquisition. The visualization provides insights about the country of origin and shows the proportions. As we can see, most of the museum's objects came from Egypt, which is probably Ancient Egypt. After that come the US, Iran and Peru. Standard bar charts proved to be the most informative and provided clear insights about the art collection. The main bias of the country of origin data is the lack of standardized names of the countries, for example, Northern France can be mentioned as France and more info can be

possibly in the object additional info, if available. As mentioned above, the standards in the object description can provide better statistics and create the base for future Semantic Web.

From the graphs we can see that the major amount of the collection came from Egypt and the United States, which probably was affected by the collection acquisition, which happened mostly in the 1910s - 1920s, when the interest to Ancient Egypt was high.

References

Mark-Jan Bludau, Marian Dörk, Frank Heidmann in their paper “Relational perspectives as situated visualizations of art collections”, Digital Scholarship in the Humanities, Volume 36, Issue Supplement_2, October 2021, Pages ii17–ii29, <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqab003>

L. Noehrer, J. Carlton and C. Jay., “Machine Learning and Museum Collections: a Data Conundrum”. August 2021, in book: Emerging Technologies and the Digital Transformation of Museums and Heritage Sites (pp.19-31), August 2021, DOI:[10.1007/978-3-030-83647-4_2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-83647-4_2)